

Clinical Instructors' Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice Regarding Evidence-Based Practice

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ABSTRACT

Background: The application of EBP has highly appreciated across healthcare disciplines to improve health care delivery. The utmost goal of nursing is the safe and compassionate patient care that can be achieved through utilization of best research evidence in making decisions for health care services. These expectations have laid the responsibility on clinical instructors to prepare their future nurses for this multifaceted role. **Aim:** Therefore, the present study aimed to determine the clinical instructors' level of knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding EBP in the Pakistani context. **Methodology:** A cross-sectional study design was adopted. Clinical instructors (n=110) from two public and private sectors nursing institutes recruited in the study by using convenience sampling technique. A structured self-administered questionnaire was utilized. Data was entered in SPSS (Version 23.0) for analysis and descriptive analysis was done. **Results:** The participants were predominantly female clinical instructors (86.4%) as compared to male counterparts. Most of the study participants (62.7%) were having Bachelor of Science in nursing degree. Study yielded the good level of knowledge among most (96.4%) of the instructors whereas about half of the study participants (50.9%) showed moderate level of practice. Moreover, underdeveloped attitude was found among less than half (47.2%) of the participants. **Conclusion:** Generally, knowledge of clinical instructors regarding EBP was high, but attitude and practice were low among the clinical instructors.

Keywords: Evidence-based practice, clinical instructors' knowledge, attitude, and practice, barriers to EBP, facilitators to EBP, teaching strategies.

Cite as:

INTRODUCTION

Evidence-based practice (EBP) has extended its significance throughout the world in recent years (Nalweyiso, Kabanda, Mubuuke, Sanderson, & Nnyanzi, 2019; Stichler, Fields, Kim, & Brown, 2011; Walker & Bukhari, 2018). The application of EBP has highly appreciated across healthcare disciplines to improve health care delivery (Hickman, Kelly, & Phillips, 2014; Mthiyane & Habedi, 2018). The EBP refers to a collaborative approach used to reach health care decisions by providing the best, current, and available solutions to the problems while caring for the clients and their families (Sherin, 2014; Shoghi, Sajadi, Oskuie, Dehnad, & Borimnejad, 2019; McInerney, & Suleman, 2010).

EBP conceptualized as clinical decision-making approach integrated with significant research evidence, clinical experience of health care providers, and clients' preferences along with their personal characteristics (Melnyk & Overholt, 2016; Paudel, Acharya, Pun, Paudel, & Arjyal, 2018; Stannard, 2019).

Internationally, the health care community is also agreed on the Melnyk and Fineout-Overholt (2017) statement that without utilizing the scientific evidence standard care cannot be provided to reduce the morbidity and mortality and to decrease the health care cost. Thereupon, the concept of EBP has been accepted as a gold standard (Mehrdad, Joolae, Joolae, Bahrani, 2012; Walker, 2020). Health care is a constantly changing system and becoming more complex with time due to increased burden of new diseases, advancement in technology and cultural changes (Kabeel & Eisa, 2016; Saldana, 2014). The nursing profession has the core responsibility to deal with this multifaceted challenge (Saldana, 2014; Shaefer & Welton, 2018). This expectation has laid the responsibility on clinical instructors to prepare their future nurses for this multifaceted challenge (Collins et al., 2018). Therefore, health care educators and clinical practitioners need to be knowledgeable, rationalized, and respond more wisely to the varying requirements of clinical practice (Mollon et al., 2012; Anaker & Elf, 2014). Thus, the emphasis is placed on the need to update health professionals' knowledge by moving away from traditional practices that are based on opinions of colleagues and peers (Alzayyat, 2014; Kyriakoulis, Patelarou, Laliotis, Wan, Matalliotakis, Tsiou, & Patelarou, 2016).

The utmost goal of nursing is the safe and compassionate patient care that can be achieved through utilization of best research evidence in making decisions about health care services (Saldana, 2014; Shaefer & Welton, 2018). Indeed, people now are aware and demand quality and standard in nursing care and nurses no longer can rely on the knowledge of textbooks, lab practices and experience only (McInerney, 2010; Alzayyat, 2014). There is a need to produce nurses who are competent in research inquiry and its application to develop their critical thinking and decision-making skills. Nursing students have to learn to integrate valid, relevant, and current research findings while providing safe and quality care to the patients (Aurang Zeb et al., 2018; Vincenten, 2019).

In addition, if higher education institutions of Pakistan intend to educate health professionals whose practice should be grounded in innovative research evidence then students' need to be introduced with learning opportunities of EBP (Muhammad, 2017). During clinical practice, nurses get opportunities to involve and discover new scientific means of patient care and ultimately lead to a change in the health system (Cioffi, 2017). Hence, the nursing instructors have to facilitate nursing students to acquire skills, knowledge, and attitude towards EBP through didactic and clinical teaching to enhance nursing practice (Warkentin et al., 2014).

There is a dire need to improve knowledge and develop positive attitude of nursing students towards EBP to encourage the implementation of EBP in the clinical practice (Hickman et al., 2014; Umarani, 2014). Therefore, the channel to inculcate the spirit of EBP into the nursing culture is to enhance first clinical instructors' own awareness, readiness, contribution, and commitment to this novel phenomenon (Malik et al., 2015; Belden, Leafman, Nehrenz, & Miller, 2012). For that reason, there is a necessity to examine the clinical instructors' individual level of awareness, attitude, and practice of EBP. Hence, the present study was designed to measure the baseline knowledge, attitude, and practice of clinical instructors regarding EBP during their clinical supervision.

Problem Statement

Lack of attention has been given to the teaching and the use of EBP in nursing education, particularly in developing countries which results in poor healthcare (Paudel et al., 2018). Many researches on EBP has been conducted in developed countries (Hung et al., 2015). Clinical instructors are expected to critically analyze current research evidence and apply EBP in their clinical supervision. However, it appears that they have had limited exposure to EBP in the undergraduate nursing programs, which often do not include any literature accessing, acquiring, and appraising skills and a sound knowledge to integrate it into clinical practice.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study was to identify the level of knowledge, attitude, and practices of clinical instructors working in public and private nursing colleges regarding EBP.

Research Question

This study answered the following research questions:

1-What is the level of knowledge, attitude, and practice of clinical instructors regarding evidence-based practice?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Evidence-based practice (EBP) is an interdisciplinary approach used to solve patient's problems combined with the best research evidence, patients' unique values, and the experience of nurse clinician (McInerney, & Suleman, 2010; Strauss, 2011; Baker, 2017; Boswell & Cannon, 2020). Evidence-based nursing is an umbrella concept in patient-centered care between the nurses, patients, and the best data derived from diverse studies (Sherin, 2014; Melnyk & Overholt, 2015; Stannard, 2019). EBP essentially requires that optimal clinical decisions in health care should be based on evidence that is valid, reliable, current, and easily accessible (Shogi et al., 2019; Bashar, 2019; Warren et al., 2016).

An introduction to the nursing research has already been included in the baccalaureate curriculum for nursing students in Pakistan (Muhammad, 2017; Ramsay, Wicking, and Yates, 2020). Initially, it was not only difficult for nursing students to understand the concept of research but it was equally challenging for nursing instructors to teach them (Lowe, 2020; Saldana, 2014). In Pakistan, the undergraduate and graduate students are relatively more inclined to learn and practice the research process rather than utilization of research findings required to enhance analytical and critical thinking skills for EBP (Muhammad, 2017; Mackey & Bassendowski, 2017; Ramsay et al., 2020). The purpose of teaching these skills is to learn to incorporate theoretical scientific knowledge in day-to-day problem solving and nursing diagnostic processes (Saldana, 2014; Ramsay et al., 2020; Warkentin et al., 2014).

Communicating the knowledge and skills of EBP to nursing students is a big challenge due to students' lack of interest in research, difficulty in analyzing and interpreting research findings as well as a lack of availability of resources to access the information (Aurang Zeb et al., 2018; AnAaker & Elf, 2014; Collins, Ross, Crawley, & Thompson, 2018). Similarly, the addition of EBP into the culture of an institution is a lengthy process that demands good administration and adequate resources (Patelarou et al., 2017; Baker, 2017) The literature reported that nursing educators understand the effectiveness of EBP but its application mostly remains a challenge in developing countries like Pakistan due to lack of proper training to translate it to the future nurses (Abu Hasheesh & AbuRuz, 2017).

Fiset, Graham, and Davies (2017) observed in their scoping review including 37 studies that EBP can be ensured by providing and implementing guidelines and checklist of procedure in the clinical area. The clinical instructors can then supervise their students while performing nursing care by using evidence-based approaches (Glen, 2016). Likewise, clinical rotations were identified as the optimal time for students to learn how to incorporate research evidence into clinical practice from the early years of their course. These trainee nurses need to be prepared for their professional roles as they are going to spend their maximum time as bedside caregivers (Sin & Bliquez, 2017). One of the big challenges which nursing educators generally face is the provision of skills that are based on scientific principles rather on the traditional methods practiced by colleagues (McInerney, 2010). On the other hand, EBP requires that nurses should plan their actions on the basis of clinically relevant researches as opposed to traditional tried and tested methods that usually are based on opinions (Alzayyat, 2014). Therefore, clinical educators no longer can rely only on content information, books, and lab practices.

Factors Facilitate the Implementation of EBP

Melnyk and colleagues (2009) debated that a shared vision and good knowledge of EBP is considered one of the facilitators which ultimately promote its use in the real world of health. A literature review was carried out by Vincenten et al (2019) including 32 case studies that were taken from twenty-four countries. The review detected the factors that affect the process of EBP. One of the four themes identified was the sound knowledge along with the skill of EBP needed to discuss, transfer, and apply it by all those contributing to undergraduate and graduate nursing education (Kim et al., & Bassendowski, 2017). Warren et al. (2016) concluded in a study that clinical nurses having higher nursing degrees, certification in EBP, and serving in leadership roles were found to be more encouraging and favorable toward the application of EBP.

Similarly, the clinical experience of the clinical instructors facilitates EBP in didactic and practical learning. A multi-institutional descriptive study with 262 clinical nurses highlighted the positive correlation between the length of clinical experience of faculty and their knowledge about EBP. The study further revealed that the nurses with less experience although exhibited a positive attitude towards the application of EBP they were still found to have less knowledge to use the phenomenon in diverse and complex situations (Al-Busaidi et al., 2019).

In furtherance of the above, a cross-sectional survey was conducted by Paudel et al (2018) in Nepal among clinical and non-clinical nursing instructors (n=172). The findings disclosed that senior faculty had generally positive attitudes towards EBP, and the faculty with more experience spent more time acquiring and appraising evidence compared to less experienced faculty. Findings further stated that there was no difference found in attitude about EBP between faculty working in clinical and non-clinical departments.

Moreover, clinical nurses' level of qualification is another perspective that expedites the use of EBP. Mehrdad et al (2012) conducted a study in Iran in which nurses and midwives (n=240) having a Bachelor's or Master's degree in nursing were included. The result of the study reported a significant statistical positive relationship between education and their level of knowledge. Nurses with Bachelor's degrees exhibited comparatively low levels of knowledge or practice about EBP as compared to the nurses having Master's degrees ($p < .001$). Besides, a substantial difference was also found by the field of study between the mean scores on knowledge, attitudes, and practice about EBP.

On the whole, the organizational culture as a facilitator to EBP initially finds the need for EBP. The organization affords tools to attain, provides a supportive environment, and at the end evaluates the outcomes concerning EBP (Schaefer & Welton, 2018; Warren et al., 2016). A study conducted in Korea with 521 clinical nurses utilizing convenience sampling identified a lack of organizational readiness leading to insufficient EBP implementation. Another study reported that organizational readiness towards the practice of EBP was significantly positively correlated with each other (Yoo et al., 2019; Worum et al., 2020).

Barriers in the Application of EBP

Many studies have informed that EBP faces certain barriers when applying to real-life health care scenarios (Greenhalgh, et al., 2014). Shayan et al., 2019) classified these barriers as departmental, nurse-related and few are interdisciplinary barriers. These barriers are mainly reported in developing countries like Pakistan (Aurang Zeb et al., 2018).

Some of the barriers to EBP in nursing education is the clinical instructors', students' and nurses' lack of knowledge in searching different databases and understanding research reports along with their lack of preparedness to use it in daily practice. Moreover, lack of content, teaching strategies, and guidelines to reach the standardization in all three nursing programs (undergraduate, graduate, and post-graduate). (Fiset et al., 2017; Melnyk et al., 2012). These barriers are inter-related and usually affect in triangulation in the nursing discipline (clinical instructors, students, & nurses) but other health professions may experience the same (Harding et al., 2014; (Skela-Savic et al., 2020).

Furthermore, a mixed-method study was carried out in Ghana among registered nurses (n=240) in a teaching hospital. The results revealed that institutional and job-related barriers are mainly hindering the implementation of EBP among registered nurses. Participants reported a lack of policy guidelines on the practice of EBP and lack of resources such as library facilities, internet, and workload as the main challenges (Atakro et al., 2020; O'Lynn et al., 2012). Likewise, two descriptive studies was conducted in Pakistan found shortage of time, lack of administrative help, the poor handiness of resources/tools, and scarcity as barriers in nursing inquiry (Aurang Zeb, 2018; Tahir, 2017).

A qualitative descriptive study was conducted in South Africa using the content thematic analysis method. The findings revealed that most of the nursing instructors are helpful and exhibited a positive attitude towards the application of EBP in academia but their level of knowledge and practice is not appropriate due to the lack of enthusiasm and commitment towards EBP (Gloria, Mthiyane & Habedi, 2018). Similarly, another descriptive qualitative study carried out with a focus group (n=46) reported a lack of competence and organization support as the chief barriers among primary care nurses (Pericas-Beltran et al., 2014).

The Outcome of the Use of EBP

Previous researches stated that the gap between obtaining evidence and its appropriate use can lead to increased cost and load on the health system (Shoghi et al., 2019; Paudel, et al., 2018). Heydari (2014) reported that nurses working in government and public institutes of Iran had been questioned for their sub-standard care given to patients and families in recent years. Literature from recent studies reported that when health care providers participate in EBP activities they feel a sense of autonomy in their decisions which ultimately leads to greater job satisfaction. In the same way, EBP empowers nurses by optimizing health outcomes (Black et al., 2015; Aurang Zeb et al., 2018).

Strategies to Teach Nursing Students about EBP

The nursing instructors are not only responsible for teaching their students the skills of scientific inquiry but also involved in generating new knowledge by using critical thinking and decision-making approaches (Chien, 2019). Some innovative and engaging teaching strategies are the solution to meet the goal of EBP integrated curricula (Sin & Bliquez, 2017; Zhou et al., 2016). Andiwatir and Betan (2019) reported that increasing knowledge and skills about critical appraisal of evidence has proved as an effective strategy to integrate the concept of EBP into clinical practice. Melnyk and colleagues recommended teaching the five steps model of EBP step by step to incorporate it into nursing education and clinical practice (2009). Melnyk et al suggested that those nurses who considered themselves good at knowledge in EBP may be utilized as a strategy to mentor the nursing students (2009). Furthermore, small group work, role play, PBL, computer classes, seminars, workshops, support the EBP knowledge

translation and practice skills (Hickman et al., 2018). Gillette and Balevi (2019) described that many opportunities for students are there to integrate evidence into practice such as clinical care guidelines, procedure technique protocols, treatment planning, care prioritization as well as case presentation.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design: A descriptive cross-sectional research design was used to assess the level of knowledge, attitude, and practice of clinical instructors regarding EBP.

Setting: Six nursing colleges in Lahore and Islamabad from two sectors (public, private) were included in the study.

Study Population: The population consisted of clinical instructors (CI's) working in the selected public and private nursing colleges (N=129).

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion Criteria: Clinical instructors having MSN/MPH or BSN/PRN degrees, working in the selected colleges, currently registered with Pakistan Nursing Council (PNC), having more than one-year clinical teaching experience either at college or clinical practice.

Exclusion Criteria: Clinical instructors on deputation/earned leave at the time of study and who are performing administrative role (not engaged in teaching)

Sampling: Convenience sampling was done to recruit study participants. Universal sample size was obtained in the study. When the total population is ≤ 100 , this same number may be taken as the sample size (Roshan Essani & Ali, 2011). Nursing instructors (N=129, n=110) involved in class-room, laboratory, and clinical instruction at the time of data collection were included in the study.

Data Collection Tool: A self-administered questionnaire was adapted from the original researcher (McInerney & Suleman, 2010) and modified to use it in the local context. The tool contained close-ended questions focusing on clinical instructors' knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding EBP.

Cut-off Scores: Modified Bloom's cut-off point was considered to set the levels for knowledge, attitude, and practice. Knowledge and practice scores were divided into three equal tertiles. The first tertile indicated poor level of knowledge and practice for scores less than 50%. The second tertile showed moderate level of knowledge and practice for scores between 50.01% to 79.9% and the third tertile represented good level for scores between 80% to 100%. While for attitude section; scores $\leq 50\%$ were considered as under-developed attitude whereas scores above 50% were labelled as developed attitudes (Gebremedhin, et al., 2018; Seid, & Hussen, 2018).

Content validity: A panel of 05 field experts checked the tool and evaluated its content and face validity. Further, the questionnaire was modified according to the expert's feedback. Most of the statements were rephrased to enhance clarity of the items.

Reliability of Tool: Calculated Content Validity Index (CVI) of the questionnaire for clarity showed 86% and for relevance is 92%.

Pilot Study: A pilot test of the questionnaire was conducted on 10% (n=11) of the sample size. Participants completed the survey in approximately 14-16 minutes. The clinical instructors who participated in pilot testing were not included in the actual study.

Data Collection Procedure: Data was collected by primary researcher. A total of 110 clinical instructors were approached in the selected colleges to complete the questionnaire. Code numbers (A, B, C, D, E, and F) were given to the nursing colleges included in the study. A unique serial number was given to each questionnaire. ID numbers were written instead of participant's name. Each questionnaire was checked for completeness by the researcher as the participants returned it.

Statistical analysis: Statistical analysis was done by using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 23. Data were collected, revised, coded, organized, tabulated, and analyzed using frequencies (f), number (n), percentage (%), mean scores, and standard deviation (SD). Data were presented in the form of tables and figures.

Ethical Considerations:

The study was approved by the Institution of Review Board (IRB) of the Shifa-Tameer Millat University. Moreover, permission was obtained from the principals of the selected nursing colleges to approach the potential participants. Verbal and written informed consent was taken before data collection. The purpose and objectives of the study were explained to the study participants. Confidentiality and anonymity of the participants and colleges were maintained throughout the study.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A total of 110 clinical instructors participated in the study. Mostly (86.4%) of the study participants were consisted of females. Less than two third (62.7%) of the participants had Bachelors' degrees. The overall mean age was reported 43.38 years (SD \pm 9.363), the age ranged between 26 to 55 years. Above one third (39.1%) of the participants were in age range of 46 to 55 years. The mean years of experience was 18.57 (SD \pm 9.736). Nearly one third (31.8 %) participants were in the experience range of 1 to 10 years. The majority (33.6%) of the participants had specialization in Critical Care Nursing, Psychiatric Nursing (10.9%), Pediatric Nursing (10%), Community Health Nursing (9.1%), Clinical education (3.8%), Ophthalmic Nursing (3.6%), and Operation Theater Nursing (2%).

Results

Table 1 Participants' Level of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice for EBP (n=110)

Levels	Knowledge	Attitude	Practice
	n(%)	n(%)	n(%)
Good	106(96.4)	-	52(47.3)
Moderate	4(3.6)	-	56(50.9)
Poor	-	-	2(1.8)
Developed	-	48(43.7)	-
Under-developed	-	62(56.3)	-

Table 1 illustrates the study participants' level of knowledge where vast majority (96.4%) of the study participants having good knowledge. While on attitude scale, nearly half (43.7%) of the participants reported developed attitudes and (56.3%) reported under-developed attitude towards EBP. Similarly, about one half (47.3%) of the participants were good at practicing EBP and another half (50.9%) of the participants were found practicing EBP moderately, whereas very few (1.8%) of the study participants scored low on the application of EBP.

Study Participants' Knowledge of Evidence-based Practice

Table 2 shows 100% scores on item 1 and item 3 whereas the rest of the item ranges from 93.6% to 98.2 %.

Table 2 Participants' Responses on Knowledge Scale (n=110)

Item Nos.	Statements	True n(%)
1	Evidence-based practice is the process of clinical decision making based on current systematic research	110(100)
2	Application of evidence-based practices leads to clinical effectiveness	108(98.2)
3	There is a need to integrate evidence-based practice in our clinical teaching and practice	110(100)
4	The components of evidence-practice are; best research evidence, clinical expertise, and patient preferences and values	103(93.6)
5	The steps in the evidence-based practice are; ask a question, search for high quality evidence, appraise and apply it and evaluate its effectiveness	107(97.3)
6	Evidence-based practice improves patients' care	108(98.2)
7	Using the current, relevant and significant evidence is an important competency in clinical teaching and practice	108(98.2)
8	Evidence-based practice keeps clinical instructors updated about new nursing protocols for patient care	107(97.3)

Study Participants' Attitude towards Evidence-based Practice

Table 3 illustrated that less than half (43.7%) of the participants showed a developed attitude towards the use of EBP and the majority (56.3%) reported under-developed attitude towards EBP. The highest mean scores (3.25 ± 0.73 , 3.22 ± 0.72) were reported on attitude item 7 stated that 'participants intend to read relevant literature to update knowledge (81.36%)' and item 8 intend to apply best available evidence findings to improve teaching and clinical practice (80.45%). The lowest mean scores (1.49 ± 0.69 , 1.96 ± 0.81 , 2.01 ± 0.75 , 2.28 ± 0.85) were reported on attitude item 3 stated that evidence-based practice is a waste of time (37.27%), item 2 participants dislike having their teaching practice questioned (49.09%), item 4 they follow traditional practices (50.23%), and item 1 could not update with new evidences because of heavy workload and lack of time (60.9%)

Table 3 Participants' Responses on Attitude Scale (n=110)

Item #	Statements	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Agree (3)	Strongly Agree (4)	
	M± SD	f(%)	f(%)	f(%)	f(%)	
1*	I could not update myself with new evidences because of my heavy workload and lack of time	20(18.2)	47(42.7)	35(31.8)	8(7.3)	2.28±0.85
2*	I dislike having my teaching practice questioned	32(29.1)	56(50.9)	16(14.5)	6(5.5)	1.96±0.81
3*	Evidence based practice is a waste of time	66(60)	36(32.7)	6(5.5)	2(1.8)	1.49±0.69
4*	I follow tried and trusted (traditional) methods rather than changing to anything new	27(24.5)	58(52.7)	22(20)	39(2.7)	2.01±0.75
5	New evidence is highly important that I make the time in my work schedule	13(11.8)	68(61.8)	24(21.8)	3(2.7)	3.01±0.72
6	I appreciate questions on my teaching and clinical practice	63(57.3)	25(22.7)	2.99±0.74	4(3.6)	18(16.4)

7	I intend to read relevant literature to update my knowledge	3(2.7)	10(9.1)	53(48.2)	44(40)	3.25±0.73
8	I intend to apply best available evidence findings to improve my teaching and clinical practice	2(1.8)	13(11.8)	54(49.1)	41(37.3)	3.22±0.72
9	The evidence I found has changed my clinical practice	2(1.8)	19(17.3)	68(61.8)	21(19.1)	2.98±0.66
10	I intend to develop skills in accessing, acquiring and appraising evidence relevant to my area of practice	4(3.6)	8(7.3)	59(53.6)	39(35.4)	3.21±0.73

Note. * = negative statements, reversed at the time of scoring

Study Participants' Practice regarding EBP

Table 4 shows that less than half (47.3%) of the participants reported a good level of practice of EBP. The majority (50.9%) revealed moderate level of practice whereas (1.8%) of the participants reported as poor in practicing EBP. The highest mean scores (4.52±0.76, 4.50±0.74) were observed on practice items 1 where majority (90.36%) of the participants knew that 'they have to apply evidence-based practice in clinical teaching and practice' and (90%) on item 2 were agreed that research evidences are useful for clinical teaching and learning. The lowest mean scores (3.31±1.07, 3.36±1.16) were reported on practice items 5 and 6 stated 'clinical instructors spend hours per week reading nursing literature (66.18%)' and they read journal articles of nursing disciplines in last month (67.27%)'.

Table 4 Participants' Responses on Practice Scale (n=110)

Item #	Statements	Never (2)	Rarely (3)	Sometime (4)	Mostly (5)	Always	M± SD
	(1)	f(%)	f(%)	f(%)	f(%)		
1	Clinical instructors have to apply evidence-based practice in clinical teaching and practice	-	18(16.4)	17(15.5)	75(68.2)		4.52±0.76
2	Research evidences are useful for clinical teaching and learning	-	2(1.8)	10(9.1)	29(26.4)	69(62.7)	4.50±0.74
3	I search literature in the form of published evidence	1(0.9)	9(8.2)	37(33.6)	34(30.9)	29(30.9)	3.74±0.97
4	Last month, I read journal articles of nursing disciplines	10(9.1)	13(11.8)	32(29.1)	37(33.6)	18(16.4)	3.36±1.16
5	I spend hours per week reading nursing literature	5(4.5)	21(19.1)	34(30.9)	35(31.8)	15(13.6)	3.31±1.07
6	My clinical teaching and practice are evidenced based	2(1.8)	9(8.2)	22(20)	44(40)	33(30)	3.88±0.99
7	To keep me up to date, I use resources such as journals, textbooks, internet, colleagues, and clinical guidelines	-	8(7.3)	13(11.8)	30(27.3)	59(53.6)	4.27±0.94
8	I use research evidences from different resources to improve my clinical teaching	-	8(7.3)	20(18.2)	38(34.5)	44(40)	4.07±0.94

9	I informally share and discuss literature/research Findings with others in my workplace	3(2.7)	12(10.9)	24(21.8)	45(40.9)	26(23.6)	3.72±1.03
10	I attend seminars, course, work-shops, conferences and trainings on evidence- based practice	2(1.8)	15(13.6)	31(28.2)	40(36.4)	22(20)	3.59±0.87

Analysis

Knowledge of EBP

The results of current study identified that majority 96.4% of the study participants' possessed good knowledge of EBP. The findings of participants' knowledge of EBP in this study was high as compared to international studies that reported lack of knowledge of EBP among the study participants (Mehrddad et al., 2012; Ammouri et al., 2014; AbuRuz et al., 2017; Ahmed et al., 2015). In researcher's point of view, the clinical instructors in the current study might have involved in research assignments, EBP projects, therefore they had greater awareness of EBP. EBP is strongly integrated within the nursing curriculum even at the undergraduate level i.e. Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN/PRN) (Malik et al., 2015). Moreover, a number of studies have shown that nurses possess higher EBP knowledge when compared to other health professionals (Wilkinson et al., 2012; Seid & Hussien, 2018). Also, previous studies have found that nurses tend to understand research terms better than other healthcare professionals and have a holistic approach toward research activities (Ammouri et al., 2014).

In addition, the literature illustrates that the study participants might rate themselves high when using the self-reported tools for data collection (West, 2014; Stichler et al., 2011). Besides, a common attribute among current and international studies was the use of self-reported questionnaires except in the Iranian study (Mehrddad, et al., 2012) that used the most robust method multiple-choice questions to assess the EBP knowledge among their study participants. Therefore, difference among the findings of current study and international study might be attributed to variation of measuring tools, contexts, and the characteristics of study participants.

Attitude for EBP

The findings in this study reported that nearly half (43.7%) of the participants showed developed attitudes. While majority (56.3%) exhibited under-developed attitudes towards EBP despite having the good knowledge of EBP. These findings of current study contradict the study done by Stichler et al. (2011) who reported developed attitudes among the majority of the study participants. This pattern is indicative that knowledge alone does not warrant change in the attitude (Soares et al., 2012). Literature states that this difference in attitude towards EBP might be due to the difficulty in fully comprehending the difference between an EBP approach and the traditional research (Stichler et al., 2011).

A considerable number (80%) of clinical instructors showed developed attitude towards appreciating the questioning on their teaching and practice. Majority (86.4%) of the participants showed their inclination to apply significant evidence to improve their practice, while (89%) view EBP positively, and (89%) demonstrated an aptitude to learn the skills of EBP process such as accessing, acquiring, and appraising the literature. The above findings of the current study are highly appreciative for developed attitude. These findings are similar to the findings of a previous studies (Jamshidi, 2016).

The findings of under-developed attitude related items in the current study reported; 56.3% participants are unable to update themselves due to heavy workload and lack of time (Mean 2.28, SD ±0.85), (80%) dislike their teaching practice questioned (Mean 1.96, SD±0.81), (92.7%) considered EBP as waste of time (Mean 1.49, SD ±0.69), and (77.2%) of the study participants follow tried and trusted methods in practice. Furthermore, the findings of our study were affirmed by a Korean study conducted by Yoo (2019) identified the lack of time and insufficient organizational readiness as the cause of low attitudes among the study participants towards EBP. Similar findings were reported by Tahir (2017) in a study

conducted in Pakistan where participants revealed the hindering factors related to learning opportunities, lack of EBP culture, and scarcity of resources. The findings were also consistent with a Jordanian Study conducted by Abu-Hasheesh and buRuz (2017) where female nurses considered EBP as the waste of time, lack of utilization of EBP due to lack of knowledge and mainly rely on traditional methods of patient care.

Practice of Participants Regarding EBP

Majority (50.9%) of the study participants were at moderate level of practicing EBP. Whereas less than half (47.3%) reported good level of practice at their workplace. These findings are contradictory with previous studies (Stichler et al. 2011; Heydari et al., 2014). In my view, the varying level of practice among above mentioned studies might be due to difference in the contexts, characteristics of study participants' and variation in clinical settings.

In addition, the current study further reported low level of evidence-based practice among study participants due to lack of skills in the application of EBP. Clinical instructors (66.18%) in the current study scored poor on searching and reading the literature. A systematic review highlighted lack of searching and reading skills, lack of understanding statistical analysis along with the work overload as barriers in evidence-based literature (Scurlock-Evans, Upton, & Upton, 2014; Malik et al., 2015).

The findings in present study reported that majority (68.2%) participants were in favor of evidence-based practice. This finding is reflective of application of evidence-based practice as a part of clinical instructors' duty and institutional policy. Further, the current study reported a significant number (89%) of clinical instructors were engaged in attending workshops and conferences, as personal and professional development is imperative for application of EBP. These findings are similar to previous studies (Zhou, 2016; Paudel et al., 2018).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The present study yielded a high level of EBP knowledge but moderate and lower level of attitude and practice of EBP. Clinical instructors with master degrees show positive attitudes and practice of EBP indicating the need for more qualified clinical instructors to promote evidence-based practices. Undoubtedly, EBP is important for accountable clinical practice. Therefore, there is a need to conduct research on this particular area, the development of resources and collaborative efforts could remove the barriers and promote EBP grounded practices.

Strengths & Limitations

This research has produced the baseline findings of EBP in the Pakistani contexts and data was collected from the multiple institutes which adds to the strength of the study. Moreover, participants' mood, attitude and personal biases at the time of data collection may have affected self-reported responses of the knowledge, attitude, and practice among clinical instructors.

Recommendation

The current research highlighted various areas for further research such as; what are the facilitators and barrier to EBP?, The impact of an influential nursing educator on fostering a positive attitude in students toward EBP. There is also a need to do research using the most robust research designs to measure knowledge domain i.e., using multiple-choice questions.

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